

ALL-ROUND TUTORSHIP APPROACH: THE WAY THEY LEARN BEST

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Abstract

All round tutorship means that all students attend and are welcomed by their neighborhoods schools in age-appropriate, regular classes and are supported to learn, contribute and participate in all aspects of the life of the school. In today's schools, teachers are working in challenging circumstances (large classes, inadequate infrastructure, lack of basic teaching and learning materials, high absenteeism, inflexible policies and curricula, low salaries, etc.), with more diverse communities of learners than ever before, they are working hard to accommodate all learners in their schools to provide quality inclusive education. All learners have needs that are common to all and needs that are unique to them as individuals. Instead of assuming there is a special tutorship for children with disabilities, teachers should use the child centered pedagogy to respond to the needs of all the learners. Inclusive pedagogy is concerned with redressing the limitations on learning that are often inadvertently placed on children when they are judged 'less able'. It does not deny differences between learners but seeks to accommodate them by extending what is ordinarily available to all, taking account the fact that there will be individual differences between them is a subtle but profound difference in approaching teaching and learning for all that is the hallmark of inclusive pedagogy. We need to take time to really observe; learn about how they learn, and engage in a continual dialogue of reflection so we can teach so they can learn. If that means changing our entire style of teaching, then so be it! It's their learning after all.

All round(inclusive education) tutorship means that all students attend and are welcomed by their neighborhoods schools in age-appropriate, regular classes and are supported to learn, contribute and participate in all aspects of the life of the school. Inclusive education means different and diverse students learning side by side in the same classroom. ... They participate in student government together. And they attend the same sports meets and plays. Inclusive education values diversity and the unique contributions each student brings to the classroom. In today's schools, teachers are working in challenging circumstances (large classes, inadequate infrastructure, lack of basic teaching and learning materials, high absenteeism, inflexible policies and curricula, low salaries, etc.), with more diverse communities of learners than ever

before, they are working hard to accommodate all learners in their schools to provide quality inclusive education. Inclusive education is ‘a process of addressing and responding to the diversity of needs of all learners through increasing participation in learning, cultures and communities, and reducing exclusion within and from education. It involves changes and modifications in content, approaches, structures and strategies, with a common vision which covers all children of the appropriate age range and a conviction that it is the responsibility of the state to educate all children’. Inclusive practices celebrate difference and require first and foremost that the child be set at centre stage. All systems are changed to accommodate the child. Inclusive education is a dynamic process. It is therefore not possible to provide a blueprint with a set of fixed skills and knowledge that all teachers should have in order to be able to teach in inclusive settings.

The term ‘Pedagogy’(tutorship) is commonly used within education to refer to the observable act of teaching together with its attendant discourse of educational theories, values, evidence and justifications. It is what one needs to know, and the skills one needs to command, in order to make and justify the many different kinds of decisions of which teaching is constituted. Pedagogy is the "how" the teaching and learning occurs. Inclusive pedagogy is defined as an approach intended to promote a culture of accommodating all and ensuring practice based on the use of diverse teaching strategies. It is associated with a connective pedagogy—that is, connecting learners with their own learning first, and then connecting their learning to the curriculum (Corbett, 2001). Inclusive pedagogy is an approach to teaching that aims to raise the achievement of all children, whilst safeguarding the inclusion of those who are vulnerable to exclusion and other forms of marginalization. Inclusive pedagogy sets out to replace traditional approaches to teaching children identified as having additional or special educational needs that are based upon the argument that such children necessarily require something ‘different from’ or ‘additional to’ that which is ordinarily available, and that what is needed can be matched to learner characteristics. While it does not deny individual differences between learners, it assumes that differences are an ordinary aspect of the human condition. Instead of providing something ‘different’ or ‘additional’ for children who experience difficulties in their learning, inclusive pedagogy seeks to extend what is ordinarily available to everybody.

• **Provide multiple ways of representation**

Children differ in the way they perceive and comprehend information. Children with sensory disabilities, learning disabilities or those from a different cultural background, for example, will approach the content differently. Using different ways of representation

allows all students to make connections within and between concepts. Using different ways of representation will increase the quality of learning for all children. Teachers can alternate between visual and auditory information, customize display areas, clarify symbols and vocabulary, illustrate through multiple media, and highlight patterns, etc.

• **Provide multiple ways of action and expression**

Children differ in how they express what they know. For example, children with speech impairments may want to express themselves through written texts rather than orally. All children use different expression styles throughout their learning process. Teachers can, for example, use assistive devices and tools for alternative communication, encourage children to explore different ways of communication and expression, and allow children to express what they learned in different ways at different times.

• **Provide multiple ways of engagement**

Children have different motivations for learning. Some children might be engaged by novelty and spontaneity, while this may frighten others who might prefer structure and routine. Some children prefer to work individually, while others like to work in groups. Teachers can offer choice and autonomy, minimize threats and distractions, facilitate coping skills, and develop self assessment and reflection.

All learners have needs that are common to all and needs that are unique to them as individuals. Instead of assuming there is a special pedagogy for children with disabilities, teachers should use the child centered pedagogy to respond to the needs of all the learners. When implementing a child centered pedagogy the local conditions and culture should be respected and taken into account. The key point we need to remember is that in order for teachers to develop a more inclusive pedagogy, they often need to begin to change their classroom behavior: where they stand, how they use resources, the way they speak to and interact with the children and the way they assess the children's learning. Key features in child-centered learning approaches used by the teachers to actively engage, include and challenge all students are:

➤ **Include Diverse Content, Materials, and Ideas**

- When you are preparing lectures, questions for discussions, assignments or exams, and case studies, include language, examples, socio-cultural contexts, and images that reflect human diversity.
- Model openness to the new ideas and questions your students bring into the course, which can broaden and deepen your own knowledge of your discipline and its

relevance. Help students understand that knowledge is often produced through conversation and collaboration among disparate points of view.

- Be aware of how your own biases, or professional training and background, may have shaped the selection of content and materials in your class. If relevant, encourage students to think critically.

➤ **Create an Inclusive Environment**

- When talking with students during class, communicate clearly—starting on the first day of the semester—about what you expect to happen in the classroom, including the ways in which you would like your students to interact, ask questions, and participate.
- In addition, set and enforce ground-rules for respectful interaction in the classroom, such as guidelines for contributing ideas and questions and for responding respectfully to the ideas and questions of others.
- Get to know your students and the individual perspectives, skills, experiences and ideas that they bring into your classes.
- Communicate high standards for student learning and express confidence that every student can achieve these standards. In addition, include structured support within your course that is designed to help all students achieve those standards.
- Show respect for all questions and comments. Use verbal and non-verbal cues to encourage participation and to challenge all students to think deeply and critically.
- Encourage students to “think out loud,” to ask questions, and to actively consider perspectives that are different from their own.
- If you are teaching about topics that are likely to generate disagreement or controversy, identify clear objectives and design a structure informed by those objectives. In addition, communicate the objectives and the structure to the students, so that they know what to expect.

➤ **Encourage a Growth Mindset**

- Foster a “growth mindset” by conveying the idea that intelligence is not a reflection of fixed, “natural” abilities, but can change and grow over time. When talking with students about their performance in class or on exams or assignments, avoid describing such performance as a sign of “natural ability” . Doing so may trigger “stereotype threat,” a phenomenon in which students’ awareness of negative stereotypes that link identity and ability can lead to depressed academic performance.
- Create an environment in the classroom or laboratory in which it is okay to make mistakes and where faltering can lead to deeper learning. At the same time, be open to

the possibility that what seems to be an incorrect answer initially may lead to shared understanding of an alternative way to answer the question.

➤ **Strive for Equality of Access to Instruction and Assistance**

- Help the students learn about academic and non-academic assistance and resources that are available. Keep in mind that all students will not be equally aware of—or equally comfortable in seeking out—academic help and resources provided. Therefore, set aside time in class to talk about these resources when needed
- Articulate and share with all students the criteria you will use to evaluate their work. When appropriate, grade with rubrics or answer keys that promote fairness and transparency. Ensure that assistance provided outside of class is equally available and accessible to all students.

➤ **Attractive and Accessible Learning Settings**

The class and school environment can support child centered learning and teaching. Child centered learning spaces are welcoming for all children, are safe for all, enable equal participation of all learners and focus on self-discovery. Although it is important to create attractive and accessible learning spaces for all, this is not the end goal, but rather a means to implement child centered learning approaches in which the right of all children to access quality education is valued and addressed.

Some features of child centered learning spaces include:

Learning Corners: set up different learning corners in your class in which children can learn independently or in small groups through self-directed learning. The corners give the students the opportunity to enrich what they have previously learned, to practice new skills and to explore new concepts.

Physical Space: ensure all children can move around freely in the class and school, work individually and in groups, and access learning resources when needed.

Class Library: books are very effective teaching aids which help children to learn new concepts, develop language and understand messages. Local books or books made by children can be just as effective as expensive children's books.

Display Areas: make a display board in the class in which you can show the work of children and provide feedback on activities. Change the display board frequently and use it as a teaching aid.

➤ **Use Feedback to Refine and Improve your Methods**

- Ask a colleague to observe your teaching and help you identify patterns in instructor-student interactions. Consider which of these patterns might be encouraging full

participation and inclusion of diverse contributions, and which might be perceived as barriers to full participation and inclusion. Identify adjustments you can make to increase full participation and to minimize or eliminate such barriers.

CONCLUSION

Inclusive pedagogy is concerned with redressing the limitations on learning that are often inadvertently placed on children when they are judged 'less able'. It does not deny differences between learners but seeks to accommodate them by extending what is ordinarily available to all, taking account the fact that there will be individual differences between them is a subtle but profound difference in approaching teaching and learning for all that is the hallmark of inclusive pedagogy. We need to take time to really observe; learn about how they learn, and engage in a continual dialogue of reflection so we can teach so they can learn. If that means changing our entire style of teaching, then so be it! It's their learning after all. In the end I want to conclude with one of my favorite teaching quotes:

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